

IMMUNITY CLAUSE AND WHITE COLLAR CRIMES: THE BANE OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The paper explores the challenges of public administration in Nigeria and identifies immunity clause and white collar crimes as factors responsible for poor service delivery in Nigeria's public sector focusing on public enterprises like the Power Holding Company of Nigeria and the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation. The social contract theory was used to provide explanations of the study. In the methodology, the study adopted the ex-post factor research design. It is a theoretical paper which builds upon results from past researches on the subject matter as such explores data from secondary sources such as internet, books and news items to support the findings. The study was restricted to the challenges of public administration in the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria, with special highlights on public enterprises like the Power Holding Company of Nigeria and the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation. Findings reveals that the major reasons for poor service delivery in the public sector in spite of

various reforms by past and present administrations, is as a result of white collar crimes which in most cases remains uncovered or overlooked, and the immunity clause which protects political leaders (and even those not covered in the Constitution) in Nigeria even long after their tenure in offices. The paper therefore suggest that to correct this anomaly, white collar crimes should be seriously addressed by ensuring that public officers are held accountable, while the immunity clause should only cover those selected offices provided for in the constitution and should not extend beyond their tenures in office, so as to allow for transparency and possible prosecution of any public office holder found guilty.

Key Words: Immunity Clause, White Collar Crime, White Collar Crimes and Public Administration

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, the interplay of white-collar crimes and the immunity clause has significantly impacted several areas of public administration, particularly in governance, resource management, and the justice system. The immunity clause, which shields certain high-ranking officials from prosecution while in office, has been exploited to shield perpetrators of corruption and other financial crimes. This has led to a decline in public confidence in government institutions and created a culture of impunity, where corrupt officials can engage in embezzlement, bribery, and other forms of financial misconduct without fear of immediate legal consequences.

White-collar crimes, such as embezzlement and procurement fraud, diversion of public funds meant for essential services like healthcare, education, and infrastructure usually leads to poor service delivery, underdevelopment, and social inequality. White-collar crimes, are particularly carried out by high-ranking officials, and in some cases political officers who are also covered by the immunity clause. This makes it difficult to tackle and further prevents high ranking officers from investigation and prosecution, as such eroding public trust in government institutions and the justice system. According to Sutherland (2017), white-collar crime is a social construct rather than a legal categorization of specific offenses. In other words, rather than the crime itself, the offender's socioeconomic status qualifies a crime as "white-collar." (Osipian, 2014) opined that the white-collar crimes that are common in the public sector are embezzlement, fraud, nepotism, clientelism, patronage, cronyism, favoritism, kickbacks, cheating, plagiarism, research misconduct, ethics and sexual misconduct, and abuse of private property.

The provision of essential services to the people in Nigeria has become so inefficient and ineffective to the extent that the citizens are disappointed in the public service, making them wonder if they actually have a government in their country. In order to ensure that the public sector is more effective and efficient in the delivery of services to the people, the government of Nigeria, past and present have continued to introduced different reforms. Most of these reforms are geared at improving efficiency, transparency, and service delivery, yet they have continued to face challenges in implementation and achieving desired outcomes. It is against this backdrop that the paper highlights how the influence of immunity clause and white collar crimes have negatively affected service delivery in the Nigerian public sector, and how they

have hindered effective and efficient service delivery across various sectors, thus impacting citizens' access to essential services and overall national development and social progress.

Literature Review

The bane of public administration in Nigeria

Ajayi & Owoeye (2017) advocate for the adoption of technology-driven solutions such as electronic revenue monitoring systems and block chain technology to track resource flows and minimize opportunities for fraud. Similarly, capacity building initiatives for regulatory agencies and anti-corruption bodies have been proposed as a means to enhance their effectiveness in combating financial malfeasance. Studies such as that by Ogujiuba & Anekwe (2017) highlights the importance of stakeholder engagement and civil society participation in promoting transparency and accountability within the oil and gas sector. The study demonstrated that increased public scrutiny and oversight can serve as a deterrent to corrupt practices and encourage greater accountability among government officials and industry players. Though many scholars have tried to identify and tackle corruption and fraud separately, and the need to fight against it, this paper identifies immunity clause and white collar crimes as the main culprits behind corrupt and fraudulent practices in Nigeria especially in the administration of public services, they act as twin concepts working together to achieve a common goal, with immunity clause shielding high ranking officers in the public sector to engage in white collar crimes, as such preventing accountability and efficiency in public administration. Parastatals in Nigeria are battling with white collar crimes of different shades such as; embezzlement, fraud, bribery, insider trading, money laundering, corruption and forgery (Payne, 2012). In the work of Sutherland (1949), white collar crime was described as such crimes often perpetrated by a person of high social status in the course of his occupation for financial benefits.

Sanusi (2003), notes that the immunity clause was made in order to enable the political office holders to have uninterrupted administration such that will allow them to work for their subjects. Many scholars have argued that the immunity clause had encouraged many states governors to engage in white collar crimes, especially money laundering. Obiora (2019) stresses that the immunity clause is a clog on the wheel of the fight against corruption in the country. The lack of immediate legal consequences provides opportunities for officials to amass wealth through corrupt means, such as embezzlement, bribery, or contract inflation, knowing they likely won't face legal challenges while in office. Immunity clause is an open-ended protection that breeds criminals in power as it gives bold latitude, with impunity to commit crime against the state and the people. This has compromised in no small measure, the integrity of public service governance in Nigeria.

Administration in Nigeria's Power Sector

Public administration in Nigeria's power sector faces significant challenges related to efficiency and performance. Despite reforms which aim at privatization and improved service delivery, it has faced challenges related to effective management, investment attraction, and ensuring reliable power supply. These measures, including privatizing of key entities and implementing policies, intends to tackle long-standing issues of inefficiency, financial sustainability, and technical losses. Yet Consumers frequently experience epileptic power supply, high costs, and poor service delivery, leading to widespread dissatisfaction. In spite of

Nigeria's status as a major oil producer, its electricity situation is worse than other West African nations. In Nigeria's capital city, Abuja, the power supply situation is complex, with varying experiences across different areas and a mix of factors contributing to the current state. The city has faced recent power outages due to facility issues, highlighting the need for infrastructure upgrades and improved maintenance. The Chairman of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), Ola Olukoyede, as reported in an article by the Nation online news by Adedamola Ogunbewon (2024), has blamed the country's inconsistent power supply on corruption within the power sector. During a visit from the House Committee on Anti-Corruption and Financial Crimes in Abuja, Olukoyede expressed concern that contractors awarded projects to supply electrical equipment frequently choose substandard materials. He explained that this practice is a key contributor to frequent equipment breakdowns, power outages, and grid collapses. In spite of knowledge about corruption within the power sector, there have been no serious efforts at uncovering this corruption or prosecuting the guilty persons behind this corruption. This in the view of the researchers shows an interplay of white collar crimes and the immunity clause. While the political office holder is shielded by the immunity clause, he uses that to protect his close ally who is responsible for embezzlements and corrupt practices going on in Nigeria's power sector, hence inefficiency in service delivery. The white collar crime, which is used to characterize a number of non-violent crimes of dishonesty is very visible in the Nigerian power sector because of series of dishonest dealings going on in the sector, and has seriously crippled proper and effective service delivery to the citizens. The crimes are committed by professionals or entrepreneurs under the veil of legitimate business activities (Brenner, 2011).

Administration in Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation

Despite being a major oil producer, Nigeria relies heavily on imported refined petroleum products due to its dilapidated refineries. The Bola Tinubu-led government introduced reforms aimed at revitalising the industry to address critical challenges in this sector. While the Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) and recent executive orders seem promising, implementation has been slow, raising concerns among stakeholders, particularly industry players, who argue that the pace of reform has been sluggish and weak. Corruption in Nigeria's oil and gas sector is a persistent issue, particularly in the capital territory, Abuja, where key regulatory and financial institutions are located. This corruption manifests in various forms, including opaque financial reporting, fraudulent contract awards, and the diversion of oil revenues. This institutional weakness has created an environment conducive to corrupt practices and inefficiency, undermining the government's reform efforts. The misappropriation in the oil and gas sector underscores systemic weaknesses in governance and accountability mechanisms. It reveals loopholes that unscrupulous individuals exploit for personal gain at the expense of the nation's prosperity (Fianka, Didi, & Ibrighademor, 2024). Data from OPEC shows that Nigeria is the only OPEC member with the lowest refining capacity utilization for many years now. In fact, as at 2021, Nigeria refines only about 5,000 barrel/day, equivalent to 1 percent of total refining capacity. Successive governments have reportedly spent significant amounts of Naira to rehabilitate, operate and maintain the refineries with no result. About N1.5 trillion was reportedly spent on non-operational refineries from 2015 to 2020, averaging 264 billion naira

annually. Yet, many Nigerians lack access to unhindered supply of fuel and experience hike in fuel price, despite fuel subsidy.

The reason for the supply crunch and price hikes is clear. As oil rich as Nigeria is, its refineries are not functioning optimally despite having a nameplate refining capacity that exceeds demand. Most of these refineries were built decades ago. Mismanagement, aging infrastructure, outlived equipment, operational inefficiency, are amongst the cause of the woes. Needless to say, corruption and diversion of money allocated for maintenance are also a big factor. These instances go on to explain the level of rapacious corruption that has consumed the moral standing and ethics of public administration in Nigeria. What this means is that a lot of public servants/government officials and anti-corruption agencies are conspirators of corruption-related activities. As such, it will be difficult to objectively tackle corruption (Igbuzor, 2015).

Effects of Immunity Clause and White Collar Crimes on Public Services

The term public service is used in understanding the public sector. Adamolekun cited in Nwizu & Nwapi (2011:20) defines the public service as the “totality of services that are organized under government authority. The public service in Nigeria is plagued by an alarming rate of bribery and corruption to the extent that it ranks high on the corruption index (Transparency international, 2018). In the Nigerian public service, a lot of public servants have little or no regard for the code of conduct which stands as its ethics. Public administration in Nigeria features lack of transparency and accountability from public workers which makes it hard for Nigerians to accurately supervise the dealings of government staff, institutions agencies, and even politicians. This ugly situation has resulted in the grave misuse of government monies by government officials, most of whom are senior public servants (Osisioma, 2018). National development is achieved when public enterprises are committed to fulfilling their public functions through provision of efficient services at all levels. Efficiency measures the performances of public enterprises in line with the enabling law that established them. This paper links this mismanagements to the twin concepts of Immunity clause and white collar crimes which though separate concepts are directly linked together. While the immunity clause helps to shield certain political officers during their tenure in office, it has been used as a tool to shield selfish politicians while they embezzle public funds with impunity on the one hand, and the white collar crimes on the other hand by high ranking officers to engage in fraudulent activities within the Nigeria’s public sector thus impairing service delivery.

The financial cost of white-collar crime is great as it constitutes threat to the continued corporate existence of government parastatals. According to Blicke (2006), involvement in white-collar crimes is influenced by different factors. White-collar crime has systematically become an international crime and has assisted the growth of other crimes like drug trafficking and street crimes, hence, developing nations like Nigeria should give due attention to the menace for the sake of national development. National development is achieved when public enterprises are committed to fulfilling their public functions through provision of efficient services at all levels. The immunity clause in Nigeria has been criticized for facilitating abuse of public office due to the lack of accountability it provides. The absence of legal scrutiny has led to a lack of transparency in governance, as officials may not be held accountable for their actions and further enhances the prevalence of white collar crimes. Before 2012, the Nigerian

government lacked a well-coordinated banking arrangement and a unified structure for handling receipts and payments from government ministries and departments across the country. As a result of this, there were so many duplicated bank accounts that were operated by government ministries (Okerekeoti & Okoye, 2017). While as at that time, the use of proliferated accounts allowed government ministries in charge to remain functional and also exercise their full rights, the practice however, did not allow for transparency and accountability in the system as in most cases, monies were missing and were not properly accounted for (Dandago, 2020). Olasunkanmi & Agulanna (2018) concluded that while the intention of including the immunity clause in the constitution is good, politicians have used the provision of the clause to the detriment of democracy and this has a direct bearing on the performance of democratic rule in Nigeria since 1999. In most cases, governors were accused of looting money worth hundreds of billions from their states amidst poverty, insecurity, unemployment and declining infrastructures and services, yet were not questioned (Falana, 2020).

Thus the immunity clause has been abused to obstruct justice, intimidate witnesses, or interfere with investigations, making it harder to uncover and prosecute white-collar crimes.

Methodology

The paper adopted the ex-post factor research design. It is a theoretical paper which builds upon results from past researches on the subject matter as such explores data from secondary sources such as internet, books and news items to support the findings. The study was restricted to the challenges of public administration in the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria, with special highlights on public enterprises like the Power Holding Company of Nigeria and the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for the study is the social contract theory. The major proponents of the social contract theory are; Thomas Hobbes, John Locke and J.J. Rousseau. The basic thrust of this theory is the fact that people who hitherto did not have government or lived under an organized state decided to form the state in order for the state to serve their basic needs. Anifowoshe (2015:95) corroborated this when he said, “according to the social contract theory, the state was created by a number of individuals voluntarily entering into a contract, the terms of which provided a political authority. As a voluntary association, however, it differed from any other because it provided for the exercise of sovereignty, the supreme power to control by coercive means, if need be, the conduct of its members”. It is on this note Burns cited in Akindele (1998:47) while defining representative democracy said it is a system whereby “all (i.e. people) elected a few to do for them what they could not do together”. The people having decided to have the state must also decide those who would operate or run the affairs of the state and in doing that, they are expected to have at the back of their mind those that would effectively take care of their interest by making life meaningful for them. This scenario explains why the social contract theory was chosen as a theoretical framework in this study. As far as this study is concerned, it offers explanations regarding the fact that the state has obligation to the citizens in respect of providing them with basic and necessary services. Though it does not explain the modus-operandi of how the services would be rendered or what should be done when the state fails in its responsibilities.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

White-collar crime harms victims directly, but also affects the broader community: it can have environmental and security implications as well as hamper governments' ability to fund public services (International Public Sector Fraud Forum, 2020). The literature highlights the significance of political interference and patronage networks in perpetuating corruption within the sector (Aiyede & Adeyemo, 2018). This emphasizes the need for comprehensive reforms that strengthen regulatory frameworks, enhance accountability mechanisms, and promote greater transparency in decision-making processes. The immunity clause is meant to protect the dignity of the office and not the individual office holder as such. This is as provided in Section 308 of the Constitution. The section applies to a person holding the office of President or Vice-President, Governor or Deputy Governor. This in recent times has enhanced corruption in Nigeria hence making the war on graft difficult to win because the act is perpetrated by policy makers themselves. Corruption distorts governance and provides perverse incentives for dysfunctional behavior as well as diminishes the quality of citizens' life by diverting funds for social service into private pockets. The fundamental requirements for effective governance therefore encompass transparency and accountability in government financial transactions. However, (Umar & Aliyu, 2017) have highlighted the push for accountability mechanisms arising from the prevailing practice in many developing nations where public budgeting remains shrouded in secrecy and is predominantly controlled by the executive branch. This is why there is a growing emphasis on the role of parliaments in budget governance and oversight of public finances, driven partly by demands for increased transparency and accountability in government financial administration (Umar, et. al., 2017)

By the foregoing it is imperative for Nigerians through the civil society to hold our leaders and high ranking officers who are responsible for providing public services accountable for any form of misappropriation of funds or poor services delivery. Combatting corruption entails holding influential individuals accountable and instituting widespread change, often necessitating a multifaceted approach. (Castillo & Gabriel, 2020) suggest that actualizing transparency allows both internal and external governance stakeholders to scrutinize, access, and influence government operations. This may involve collaborating with civil society, local communities, and international organizations, while concurrently addressing issues at both the national and global levels. Such comprehensive efforts can bring about tangible improvements in the lives of citizens (Emmanson, & Ajayi, 2020). Immunity clause must as a matter of necessity be exercised within the coffers of offices provided for (presidents and their vices, governors and their deputies) as provided in the constitution and should not in any way be used by politicians to shield their appointees in top positions in the public sector who are engaged in fraudulent activities.

CONCLUSION

The paper brought to bear the glaring challenges which have arisen within Nigeria's public sector due to the twin concept of immunity clause and white collar crimes. The researchers highlighted on how these two concepts have contributed to increased inefficiency and lack of accountability thereby crippling public administration, particularly in the power sector and in the oil and gas sector. The paper maintained that to combat these two issues, the people must

as a matter of necessity hold these officers accountable in any case of poor service delivery, ensuring that there is a review on the immunity clause which the political officers enjoy while in office. By promoting transparency in revenue collection and expenditure management, governments can mitigate opportunities for misappropriation (Transparency International, 2023). Citizens and important state holders should be empowered to hold officers in top ranking positions accountable for any form of inefficiency in service delivery. Empirical evidence from studies such as that of Ogujiuba & Anekwe (2017) highlights the importance of stakeholder engagement and civil society participation in promoting transparency and accountability within the oil and gas sector. The study demonstrated that increased public scrutiny and oversight can serve as a deterrent to corrupt practices and encourage greater accountability among government officials and industry players hence further reducing the negative influence of immunity clause and white collar crimes on public administration

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommends that;

The decision to grant immunity should be reviewed by an independent body or official to ensure that it is justified and not a result of political influence or other improper considerations so as to be able to address the issue of white collar crime squarely

Accountability and transparency are fundamental principles that ensure integrity in governance and effective service provision. Consequently for there to be effective service delivery, the citizens of Nigeria must hold their political office holders and top ranking officials in key service providing companies accountable for any failure or poor service delivery. This could be through protest or refusing to pay for services that is considered unsatisfactory to people until they open up to them about the systemic failures and account for how monies allocated for key projects were utilized.

Constitution should be reviewed stating that qualification for people vying for offices of the president and their vice, the governors and deputies should be such that anyone who has a pending criminal case, especially bothering on fraud, embezzlement or corruption charges should not be allowed to contest until such cases are cleared.

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